

ROBUST

CRISIS GOVERNANCE IN TURBULENT TIMES

Overview of existing robustness strategies, incl. approaches for diagnosing turbulent problems and developing a strategic mindset for robustness

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1. Introduction

Western societies are facing an unprecedented high frequency of socioeconomic, political and humanitarian crises that tend to heighten the level of societal turbulence. This is augmented by the complex interaction between local, national and international dynamics triggered by new technologies, cultural and socioeconomic globalization, and the destabilization and transformation of social and political identities and alignments. As a result, *political leaders and administrative managers spend more and more time putting out small and big fires*. This has two negative consequences: First, there is hardly any time for formulating long-term societal goals and engaging in continuous efforts to find the right means to achieving them. Second, public officials tend to create all kind of problems for themselves and for society as a whole when they deal with turbulent problems under great uncertainty and acute time pressure. To illustrate, the alarming climate crisis has only received scant attention during the COVID-19 pandemic that was followed by first a refugee crisis and then an inflation crisis, and during the pandemic many governments were responsible for interventions that were later judged to violate existing laws and constitutional principles. The Danish government's unlawful decision to kill all minks in Demark to prevent mutations is a case in point.

The ROBUST project aims to provide new tools for diagnosing the many small and big fires as an instance of *turbulence* that may or may not be induced by crisis. It also presents a new governmental strategy for how to deal with turbulence by creating *robust governance* that provides an alternative to the pursuit of agility and resilience that either tends to sacrifice stability of the alter of innovation or to maintain the status quo ex ante that might neither be attractive nor feasible. The genealogy and different meanings of the concepts of turbulence and robustness has been presented in D2.1 that also defines the way that these concepts will be used in the ROBUST project and provides 'proof of concept' through engagement with the crisis management literature and dialogue with practitioners. Building on this, D2.2 aims to reflect on how academics and practitioners can study the robust governance of turbulence.

Assuming that we will encounter growing turbulence in the future and that robust governance responses will be in high demand, both researchers and practitioners must be able to diagnose turbulent situations, analyze the efforts to provide robust governance responses, and assess the combined impact of different response strategies. While researchers often conduct a *retrospective analysis* of the efforts to create robust answers to turbulence in order to learn from different experiences and formulate and test hypotheses, practitioners are involved in continuous efforts to deal robustly with turbulent problems based on a *prospective analysis* of what could and should be done to preserve key functions, goals, and values in the face of unpredictable dynamics.

Whether retrospective or prospective, the analysis of the robust governance of turbulence can be divided into the five stems shown in table 1.

Table 1: Five steps in the analysis of robust governance of turbulence

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| <ol style="list-style-type: none">1) Detect, diagnose and explain turbulent events and developments2) Identify the actors engaged in interaction to prepare robust solutions3) Analyze the systemic, organizational, and actor-related conditions for robustness4) Study the choice and combination of different robustness strategies5) Evaluate the impact of different robustness strategies |
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The *first step* is to *detect, diagnose and perhaps even explain turbulent events and developments*. The public sector confronts a wide array of simple and complex problems as well as a growing number of turbulent events and developments that become problematic for organizations and their environments, but how can we tell the difference between different types of problems and predicaments, and how can we make sense of turbulence when we see it?

The *next step* in the analysis is to *identify the manifold actors* who are facing the heightened level of turbulence and who may contribute to the design of robust governance and then to *analyze their interaction* and the institutional arenas that support knowledge sharing, pluricentric coordination and collaborative problemsolving. Who are the actors and how do they exchange and pool their different assets such as experience, knowledge, ideas and tangible resources in an effort to make sense of and address a heightened turbulence?

The *third step* is to look at how actors involved in the design and redesign of robust governance solutions *draw upon systemic, organizational, and actor-related rules and resources* that will condition their interaction and the formulation of their response strategy when facing turbulent problems. It is essential to analyze the context-dependence of the more or less collaborative efforts to forge robust responses to turbulence in order to determine the room of maneuver of situated actors engaged in designing robust governance responses to heightened societal turbulence.

The *fourth step* is to analyse the *choice and combination of different robustness strategies* and track their development over time as they attempt to respond to unpredictable dynamics. What strategies are used, when and how, and how are they combined in an effort to match rapidly changing circumstances as well as conflicting social, economic, and political demands?

The *final step* is to *evaluate the impact of the robustness strategies* that have been applied at different points in time. Robust governance does not strive to provide an optimal or perfect response because turbulence presents us with a multidimensional and constantly moving target and force us to take decision under uncertainty and time pressure. However, it is perfectly possible to evaluate whether the chosen robustness strategies were supported by well-informed analyses and arguments, enjoyed widespread support, were properly implemented, produced expected outcomes, and contributed to maintaining core public functions, goals, and values.

While these five analytical steps do not exhaust the long list of interesting questions that researchers and practitioners may want to ask, they provide us with the key building blocks to be used in retrospective and prospective analysis of the attempt to pursue robust governance strategies in the face of turbulence. D2.2 aims to detail the five steps presented above in order to provide a heuristic that allows researchers and practitioners to analyse the endeavor to respond robustly to turbulence. The analysis is crowned with a sketch of the ultimate condition for creating a European-wide capacity for robust governance in times of turbulence namely, the development of a robust mindset.

2. Detecting, diagnosing, and explaining turbulence

While crisis calls for crisis management aiming to contain, mitigate, counteract, and compensate its negative consequences, heightened turbulence calls for robust governance. The fact that crisis and turbulence often feed into and reinforce each other makes it difficult for governments to know how to respond. To further clarify how public governors can *detect* a situation of heightened turbulence, we shall first consider the situation where a crisis may or may not enhance turbulence, and then consider

the case of heightened turbulence where there is no triggering crisis, although a crisis may be a result of enduring turbulence.

A financial crisis may begin with the collapse of one big bank that takes other banks and ultimately draws down the entire financial market. A refugee crisis may be triggered by war, draught-induced famine, or some radical regime-change that send waves of refugees to camps in neighboring countries. A pandemic may be sparked by a manufactured or natural mutation of a known virus that spread through one or more hotspots. Such crisis events may threaten the financial sector and the prospect of stable economic growth, the social and political stability of countries receiving a large number of refugees, or the ability of the health sector to provide care for a growing number of sick. There might be a critical turning point where the central government actors do not know whether the crisis will be fatal or manageable. Proper crisis management under the right circumstances may succeed to contain the crisis and to mitigate or offset its negative effects with only a minor increase in the overall level of societal turbulence. A collapsed bank may be bought by another bank, the International Red Cross may step in to help and distribute arriving refugees, and isolation of the first disease cases and lockdown of the city in which the outbreak occurs may help to prevent a pandemic. In these cases, crises emerged but were successfully managed.

In other situations, crises are not easily fixed and impossible to contain. They soon start to spill over into other sectors and domains where they create new and unforeseen problems and challenges. A bank crisis may lead to the collapse of the housing market, cascading evictions and foreclosures, a plummeting stock-market, rising unemployment, etc. The sudden influx of a large number of refugees may foster a humanitarian crisis, financial strain on the public sector, competition for local jobs and resources, xenophobic protests and demonstrations, etc. The surprising arrival of a pandemic may overcrowd the health sector, lockdown entire countries and cities, make people lose their business and income, enhance food shortages, create loneliness, increase public debt, etc. As the repercussions of crises spread to wider areas of society, the demand for government action increases and some of the government responses may have unintended negative consequences that spark a series of small and large fires that in turn trigger new demands. Even if the threat of new bank collapses is over, the influx of refugees has come to a halt, and the number of infected people is going down, public governors may find themselves in the midst of a heightened societal turbulence since the initial events have given rise to a whole set of unpredictable dynamics.

Public governors may detect a situation of heightened societal turbulence in three ways. *First*, an unexpected and troubling situation has emerged. This is evidenced by the sudden proliferation of unpredicted and changing problems, warning signals, and negative outcomes that require public attention and prompt government action. The surprising emergence of disruptive problems and challenges and their unpredictable flux and spill-over effects makes it clear to public decisionmakers that they are not only facing a set of problems that is cognitively and politically complex, but also a bundle of problems that are characterized by temporal mutation.

Second, as the turbulent problems multiply and continue to change, it becomes clear that some of the core functions, goals, and values of the public sector can no longer be maintained based on its current modus operandi. For example, a lockdown of public institutions may prevent job center workers to carry out mandatory talks with unemployed people or make it impossible to host homeless people in shelters where they sleep in bunk beds in large dormitories. Hence, it becomes clear that the current modus operandi of the public sector is problematized by the unpredictable dynamics that call for new ways of delivering services and pursuing political goals. The much-needed changes in the

modus operandi cannot be decided based on prediction of the future but must seek to respond to what can be observed in an uncertain and changing environment.

Finally, a closer analysis of the unexpected, troubling, and increasingly unbearable situation reveals that the observed problems, warning signals, and negative outcomes are caused by a complex and dynamic interaction between one or more crisis events and their contingent context giving rise to manifold repercussions. A myriad of changing events and developments interact, merge, and reinforce each other and seem to produce new unexpected and troubling events. The increasingly tumultuous situation tends to generate new demands for interventions and compensations, growing social and political tensions, and perhaps even maladaptive governance practices that make the situation even more problematic.

It is often easier to detect crisis-induced turbulence than self-perpetuating turbulence resulting from the interaction between a large number of relatively independent events, demands, and developments that produce problems, stress and disruption. Crisis-induced turbulence begins with a big splash, which generates waves of unforeseen repercussions that continue to grow and overflow the valley. However, heightened turbulence may also come creeping as seemingly unrelated problems, conflicts, and negative developments continue to grow, multiply, and reinforce each other to create a disruptive and tumultuous period in which policy execution and goal attainment becomes difficult and changes in the modus operandi of the public sector is needed. Rising turbulence may be further stimulated by adaptive responses that worsen the problem instead of mitigating it. The construction of desalination plants to adapt to drinking water shortages in poor neighborhoods leading disproportionately high cost for low for water users is a case in point.

An example of a creeping and self-perpetuating turbulence is the 1978-79 'winter of discontent' in British politics that was constructed in politically opportune ways and later has received an almost mythological status (Hay, 2010). Against the wake of cultural and ethnic clashes involving skinheads and punks, widespread strikes by private and public sector trade unions, including local wild cat strikes, caused great public inconvenience, exacerbated by the coldest winter in 16 years, and fostered political disputes within the governing Labour party and with the Conservative opposition led by Mrs. Thatcher who won the subsequent election. A confluence of different problems such as cultural change, the demise of corporatism, the end of Keynesianism, and the rise of the new right created a highly turbulent predicament.

To detect this kind of creeping and self-perpetuated turbulence, a large number of problems and challenges and their mutual interaction and spill-over effects must be explored and assessed on a regular basis since what appears to be a few simple problems may later develop into complex problems, which in turn may become more and more unstable and changing and give rise to a growing turbulence. Problems may also lose their turbulent character over time and become complex or even simple problems. To illustrate, the COVID-19 pandemic gradually became less turbulent and called for a stable rather than dynamic resilience (Cristofoli et al., 2022).

In sum, crisis-induced and creeping turbulence have different roots as the former starts with a clearly observable crisis situation that generates a set of internally related repercussions. The latter results from the gradual and less directly observable proliferation of problematic, stressful and disruptive events, demands and developments that multiply through spill-over effects and are accelerated by maladaptive responses. However, no matter how turbulence is produced, it is experienced as unexpected dynamic that undermine public service provision and goal achievement and thus call for public response.

When public organizations and their supporting network have detected a heightened level of societal turbulence, the next task becomes to *diagnose* the turbulent events and developments to learn more about their form and character (see Arvidsson, 2014). Turbulence is a moving target, but it might be relevant to assess the scope of turbulence and the conditions for its containment or spread.

Turbulence may be internal to an organization, pervade an entire policy area, or cut through policy areas, sector boundaries, governance levels and national borders to become a near-global phenomenon. The scope of turbulence may expand or shrink over time. Much depends on the ability to contain turbulence. New unexpected events may either facilitate or prevent the containment of turbulence.

It is also important to analyze the varying degrees of adversity of turbulent events and developments. Is turbulence merely annoying because it disrupts a planned set of actions? Is it creating a growing amount of stress for the members of one or more organizations and their organizational leadership? Or is turbulence seen to constitute a threat to well-established social, political and economic systems or to national or global security? The degree of adversity will tend to determine how much attention the turbulent events and developments will receive and how many resources will be invested in developing a response.

Another aspect of turbulence that calls for analysis is the varying degree of novelty of the emerging turbulence and the existence of relevant past solutions. Is the tumultuous unfolding of unpredictable events and developments similar or dissimilar to previous experiences? Wherein lies the newness and what is its impact? These questions are important because the answers determine the ability to draw on modified versions of past solutions and the need to come up with innovative solutions.

The unpredictable and volatile dynamics deprive us of the ability to forecast turbulent events and developments. Modelling the complex interactions between a plethora of disruptive events, surprising developments, unexpected repercussions and changing demands is impossible. However, decisionmakers may still create, discuss and evaluate alternative trajectories of turbulent events and developments in order to try to stay ahead of the game by thinking through different best- or worst-case scenarios and what these scenarios require in terms of new and changing responses (Schultz, Crews and Lum, 2012). The scenarios may be proven wrong by reality. Nevertheless, they may help decisionmakers to meet the future with an open mind because they demonstrate the need to keep future options open.

A last point in the diagnostic analysis of turbulence is assessment of the likely endurance of the turbulent predicament. Turbulent predicaments come and go unexpectedly. Nevertheless, the governance response of the actors placed in the eye of the storm may in part depend on their estimated endurance. If turbulent events and developments are expected to blow over or be quickly fading, the commitment to finding adequate but costly responses may be less than if turbulence is on the rise and likely to continue into the future. A high degree of adversity may, of course, prompt actors to scale up their response even if the turbulence predicament is deemed to be short-lived. As such, researchers and practitioners may want to study what different actors think about the endurance of turbulence and how it influences their actions.

It is by no means easy to make a precise diagnosis of the different dimensions of turbulence because of its unpredictable dynamism. The diagnosis will change over time and may also be ambiguous as it reflects the ambiguity of turbulence. Moreover, real actors engaged in diagnosing a turbulent predicament may disagree about the diagnosis or the most prevalent diagnosis may be contested.

The analytical endeavor to diagnose turbulence by describing its inherent features provides us with a better understanding of what we have in front of us. This begs the question of how to *explain* turbulence. While it is impossible to fully explain the movements in a flock of birds flying in the sky, a crowd of children in a playground, or troops engaging in skirmish, we may meaningfully enquire into the necessary and sufficient conditions of the complex movements. Birds gather in big flocks when the season change and it is time for migration, children may come to a playground to play tag as a part of birthday party, and troops move around because they are aiming to take control of a city. Societal turbulence can be subjected to the same type of explanatory analysis. Hence, we may ask what triggered a sudden heightening of the normal level of turbulence in society. As explained in D2.1, societal turbulence may be caused by a crisis that remains uncontained despite different authoritative crisis responses and therefore has widespread repercussions that jump from one area to another and generate a cascade of disruptive events, developments and demands. However, as we have seen, there is also another possibility, namely that turbulence is triggered by a few independent political, economic and social events and developments that give rise to maladaptive responses that then feed the turbulent events that expand and grow in intensity and magnitude.

Following this argument, the analysis of turbulence should aim to explore the conditions for containing a sudden political, economic, or social crisis and seek to unravel the spill-over mechanisms and feedback loops between different events, developments and demands that may exacerbate and deepen the overall experience of turbulence. Attention should also be paid to the role of maladaptive responses to growing societal turbulence that may fuel a self-accelerating process of growing turbulence.

3. Actors engaged in interaction to prepare and advance robust governance

In periods of heightened turbulence, people tend to look to government for an authoritative response that can reduce or eliminate the disruptive impact of turbulence (Rosenthal and Kouzmin, 1997). Depending on the organizational structure of government and the level of devolution of political and administrative power, people will have different expectations to the role of local, regional, national and supranational government agencies.

The overall role of government and its ability to respond to rising turbulence will tend to depend on its organizational capacity, democratic legitimacy and the national tradition for government intervention in society and the economy. Some countries may even have laws and contingency plans determining when and how various parts of government will deal with different combinations of crisis and turbulence. The rules may also determine how public agencies will collaborate with private actors, local neighborhoods, citizens, etc. to respond to critical levels of turbulence where basic functions, goals and values are problematized (Smith, 2003). Exactly because turbulence is characterized by a widely distributed interactive complexity, the response to turbulence is also likely to be distributed. Different public agencies will respond in diverse ways to turbulent events and will tend to involve different kinds of societal actors in order to mobilize additional resources and extend their reach into those parts of the private sector that public agencies in liberal democratic countries can hardly affect (Scognamiglio et al., 2022). The result tends to be a hybrid form of governance where hierarchical forms of government may provide the initial response, but then draws on market forms of governance

to involve private contractors and creates collaborative arenas where relevant and affected actors contribute to the design of joint solutions.

The interactions between the public, private and civic actors involved in responding to turbulence may take different forms. As such, it is worth paying attention to the shifting emphasis on knowledge sharing, pluricentric coordination and collaborative problemsolving (Brown and Keast, 2003). *Knowledge sharing* involves the exchange and pooling of different forms of knowledge, information, and experience. By making knowledge freely available to a wider group of actors, their performance may improve because their actions have a better knowledge foundation, thus allowing actors to absorb new knowledge (Wang and Noe, 2010). *Pluricentric coordination* aims to align a plethora of sectors, organizations, and initiatives through collaborative interaction to reduce conflicts and create synergies and prevent gaps and overlaps in service delivery. Instead of relying on either the iron fist of hierarchical forms of government or the invisible hand of the market, pluricentric coordination relies on networked communication and attempts to construct a common meaning and storyline that reflects the different perspectives of the actors (Pedersen, Sehested and Sørensen, 2011). Finally, *collaborative problemsolving* involves joint agenda setting and problem definition, circulation, discussion, and cross-fertilization of ideas for solutions, mutual learning and design and testing of prototypes, and the formulation of a joint implementation plan. The collaborative approach to problemsolving benefits from the 'collective wisdom' (Landemore and Elster, 2012) and 'swarm intelligence' (Gloor, 2006) of a group of diverse actors and aims to avoid conflicts by defining the problems in ways that facilitate the formulation of solutions that allow most actors to win (Basadur et al., 2000).

In the analysis of collaborative problemsolving, special attention should be afforded to how knowledge is negotiated between political decisionmakers, scientific experts and lay actors (Kuhn, 2002). While political decisionmakers may want to base their decisions on scientific expert advice, they often find this advice to be difficult to understand and based on too many reservations. Moreover, politicians seek advice on what the best action is, while scientific experts are more interested in being scientifically correct and reluctant to recommend particular actions. In this situation, mutual trust building is important and may facilitate the development of a joint understanding of problems and viable solutions. However, when politicians and scientists have negotiated their understanding of problems and solutions, the problem becomes how to get lay actors such as private businesses, civil society organizations and citizens on board. If lay actors are presented with solutions in the form of a *fait accompli*, they may become obstinate, criticize the solutions, and organize protests. Involvement of lay actors in the negotiations may help to mitigate conflict and establish a common understanding of problems and solutions but may not always be possible. Hence, analyzing the how the room of manoeuvring is exploited to facilitate a broad knowledge negotiation is crucial.

Another prominent issue that calls for analytical attention is how actors at multiple levels and from different sectors interact with one another (Bache and Flinders, 2004). The problem here is that public and private actors from various levels and sectors may have very different views of what constitutes the problem and what a feasible solution looks like. Hence, conflicts may arise and call for mediation. Moreover, there is often a limited tradition of multi-level and cross-sector interaction between public and private actors. The standard pattern is that higher-level authorities send their messages downwards without expecting any reply, let alone the initiation of a constructive dialogue with partners. In much the same way, the public sector tends to communicate with the private sector without expecting feedback and dialogue. Private business or citizens who are critical of government

initiatives will use the mass media to voice their criticisms. However, in countries and some supranational systems such as the EU, there will be institutional mechanisms facilitating two-way dialogue. Hence, studying the drivers and barriers to multi-level and cross-sector dialogue is a key task.

The analysis of the different forms of interaction between relevant and affected actors aiming to address the wide-ranging repercussions of heightened turbulence will benefit from studying the platforms and arenas that may scaffold knowledge sharing, pluricentric coordination and collaborative problemsolving (Ansell and Gash, 2018). Platforms are semi-permanent infrastructures that support the formation, adaptation, and multiplication of temporal arenas for problem-focused interaction. While platforms provide attractive storylines, organizational templates and resources that make it easy to form arenas when they are wanted and needed, arenas are institutional frameworks supporting concrete interaction through joint agenda setting, ground rules for interaction, means of communication and procedures for executing joint decisions. Interestingly, new social media may play an important role in crisis communication, thus fostering communication about the changing nature of societal disruptions and mobilizing citizens in crisis response (Reuter, Hughes and Kaufhold, 2018).

4. Exploiting the institutional conditions for robust governance responses

The experience of heightened turbulence prompts the search for robust governance responses, but there is no guarantee that such a robust response is within the reach of the public and private actors engaged in the search for solutions. The ability to design and implement robust governance solutions depend on several systemic, organizational, and actor-specific conditions that are difficult to change in the short run and therefore provide a specific set of drivers and barriers that the actors must consider. The experience of turbulence itself may function as both a driver and barrier in the search for robust solutions. On the one hand, it prompts governance actors to adapt and innovate in the face of new and changing problems, challenges and demands, while on the other hand, turbulence may put the actors under heavy pressure, triggering defensive attempts to maintain their habits, routines, and procedures. However, we shall here focus our attention on the institutional factors that condition the governance actors search for robustness.

The analysis of the systemic conditions supporting and/or hampering robust governance responses should pay attention to three important balances. The first balance is between the traditional structural, legal and regulatory rigidities of the public sector that tend to reduce its ability to produce robust responses and the unfreezing of these rigidities in a turbulent situation where new structures and procedures are invented and the old ones tend to play a lesser role. Hence, control-based hierarchies, administrative siloes and the focus on compliance with bureaucratic rules and measurement of performance results tend to narrow the room for much-needed adaptation and innovation in turbulent times. However, rising turbulence and 'crisis awareness' seem to create an extra-ordinary situation where governance actors are willing to break with established rules, procedures and habits and to accept a higher level of cognitive and organizational dissonance. This may open a window of opportunity for the advancement of robustness governance that exploits new opportunities to enhance flexibility and innovation.

The second balance is between the attempt of governments to promote institutional integration across agencies and levels of authority and the requisite variation and differentiation within the public

sector. While integration striving for coherence and uniformity may limit the efforts to foster robust responses in times of turbulence, organizational differentiation allows different public agencies to have different goal interpretations, operational priorities, and time horizons, thus facilitating flexible adaptation and collaborative innovation.

The third balance is between the organizational decoupling between different levels of authority within a multi-level governance system characterized by low trust and high conflict and a well-coupled system that supports the ability to scale governance responses to mobilize multiple concerns and resources in the production of robust solutions. Scaling does not only involve integration based on streamlining but may also facilitate the exploitation of different competences and ideas. Ideally, well-coupled multi-level governance may both facilitate top-down and bottom-up prompting of robust action as well as joint coordination of actions. This is what the US Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) is striving for.

The analysis of the organizational conditions supporting and/or hampering robust governance responses may also scrutinize the impact of some important balances. First, the balance between internal specialization between public agencies that may enhance robustness and the lack of coordination between specialized organizational units that might undermine it. Second, the balance between spending time in secondary organizational structures with a networked character, which promotes flexibility and innovation, and spending time in primary organizational structures that focus on authoritative decisionmaking. Third, the balance between complex and loosely coupled organizations with a hybrid character that may generate robustness and simple and tightly coupled organizations based on shared goals and understandings that may be locked into a particular modus operandi. Fourth, the balance between the organizational capacities needed to deal with emergence, build resilience and support decentralized problemsolving and the capacities needed to ensure performance, compliance and centralized execution and accountability. Finally, obtaining a good balance between the need to change the periphery of public institutions while maintaining the stability of the core institution is a significant challenge.

The analysis of the actor-related conditions supporting and/or hampering robust governance responses should focus on the balance between the ability of organizations to precisely define what is appropriate action for different members of the organization and the ability of actors to reinterpret the more or less ambiguous logic of appropriate action and bend it to fit shifting circumstances. Another important balance that requires careful analysis is the one between a static resource allocation between distributed actors and a dynamic resource allocation based on negotiation that allows actors to get access to a range of different resources depending on the situation in which they find themselves. Finally, it is crucial to study the balance between contexts where public officials in organizations with good reputation and symbolic significance are trusted by the citizens and other contexts where citizens distrust government and are unlikely to comply with shifting governance instructions.

The conditions for robust governance in the face of turbulence depends on a series of institutional balances that can be difficult to change in the heat of the moment through intentional reform that aims to tilt the balance in favor of robust governance. Over time the balances may be changed based on ongoing experiential learning. If the learning takes place during a period of rising turbulence, the crucial question is how to ensure learning retention and how to prevent the lessons drawn during a turbulent situation from becoming a new dogma that will limit the future capacity to foster a flexible response to turbulence (Bentzen and Torfing, 2022). Studying the role of learning, learning retention and the flexible use of learning to improve the conditions for developing robust responses to

turbulence is fundamental and may simultaneously focus on the individual, organizational and systemic level.

Ultimately, the study of the systemic, organizational, and individual conditions of situated actors to govern robustly will allow researchers and practitioners to assess the room of maneuver for governance actors who aim to use and combine different strategies for robust governance. This room might be expanding or shrinking as a result of learning and the impact of turbulence that may simultaneously unravel the institutional constraints and remove the slack that actors may need to transform the institutional conditions for robust action.

5. Combining different robustness strategies based on situational analysis

Governance actors may govern robustly and meet the challenge of turbulence by pursuing robust strategies without ever using the notion of robustness and without being acquainted with any research on robustness. The concept of robust governance is an analytical construct that offers a lens by which we can describe the strategies and actions of real actors as more or less robust in the sense of contributing to upholding key functions, objectives and values through flexible adaptation and proactive innovation of the modus operandi of the public sector.

Studying governance actors' attempt to produce robust responses to turbulence may begin with the analysis of how their efforts to *remove the barriers to and build support* for flexible adaptation and proactive innovation. A key point here is to study the extent to which critical reflection, joint learning and distributed action is promoted by key governance actors in a concerted attempt to achieve robust governance. It is paramount that governance actors spend time reflecting on what they are doing, what the drivers and barriers for rapidly designing and implementing new and promising solutions are, and how experimenting with new forms of governance can help them do better. Joint learning based on lessons learned and the circulation of new ideas and procedures is also important to build capacities for robust action and so is the cultivation of an organizational culture that allows local actors to improvise, follow new leads and act based on rapid learning. Careful analysis of these efforts serves to establish the ability of the actors to create an environment that support robust action.

The next step in the analysis is to look more closely on how governance actors *choose and combine robustness strategies*. As described in D2.1 and shown in table 2, there is a broad repertoire of robustness strategies such as redundancy, multivocality, vigilance, flexible adaptation, scaling, modularity, proactive innovation and collaboration. Empirical studies may reveal what influences the choice and combination of these and other robustness strategies. Factors that may shape the decisions of the governance actors include: the actors' own past experiences with one or more robustness strategies; joint reflections about risks and potential gains related to different strategies; conflicting social, economic and political interests; isomorphic pressures from above, other jurisdictions or new employees; and the above-mentioned systemic, organizational, and actor-specific drivers and barriers.

Table 2: Overview of robustness strategies

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none">a) Redundancy, slack, and buffering: <i>'Keep something in your back pocket'</i>b) Multivocality and ambidexterity: <i>'Keep your options open'</i>c) Vigilance: <i>'Prepare to be surprised'</i>d) Flexible adaptation: <i>'Stay ready to adapt'</i>e) Scaling and scalability: <i>'Get ready to plug-and-play'</i>f) Modularity and bricolage: <i>'Recombine, reuse, and repurpose available tools'</i>g) Proactive real-time innovation: <i>'Be ready to improvise, probe and learn'</i>h) Coordination and collaboration: <i>'Rapidly convene actors and build trust'</i> |
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The choice and combination of robustness strategies must be based on an analysis of 'the situation' that is likely to change in unexpected and unpredictable ways. Therefore, the study of the pursuit of different robustness strategies should analyze the impact of changing circumstances on the relative and shifting weight of different robustness strategies within the overall package of robust governance.

The strategies described above for dealing robustly with turbulence overlap a great deal. For example, the calls for keeping your options open, staying flexible, scaling operations and resources, recombining and repurposing resources, and improvising all share a certain family resemblance. At the same time, each of these strategies adds something distinct to our understanding of robust governance. This observation raises the question of how these different strategies may fit together and how they may be fruitfully combined over time.

The overarching concern when seeking to combine strategies for robust governance is the need to simultaneously handle variability, speed, and uncertainty in the problem setting. The different robustness strategies make different contributions to this key ambition. Exploiting 'redundancy, slack, and buffering' and aiming for 'multivocality and ambidexterity' are neighboring strategies that allow public governors to deal with sudden trouble and extraordinary conditions while continuing to deliver most the usual services and mandatory forms of regulation and to do so in ways that keep future opens open. 'Vigilance' is a strategy that prepares public governors to be surprised by allowing them to look for and assess weak and emerging signals of rising turbulence, and 'flexible adaptation', 'scale and scalability', and 'modularity and bricolage' are strategies that facilitate flexible use of all available tools in designing and continuously modifying solutions in response to unpredictable dynamics. 'Proactive real-time innovation' is useful in situations where adaptation of existing solutions is not enough to uphold core public functions, objectives, and values. Finally, 'coordination and collaboration' aim to combine and give direction to distributed actions and to involve relevant and affected actors in processes of on-going contestation and negotiation that facilitate revision of the current course of action in the light of disturbance and ongoing changes in the nature and character of the problem.

There is no 'one best way' of selecting and combining the strategies for robust governance. While 'vigilance' is always a good thing and both 'redundancy, slack, and buffering' and 'multivocality and ambidexterity' are important tools for expanding the room of maneuvering for public governors, it is not always clear when and how to combine different aspects of these strategies with 'flexible adaptation', 'modularity and bricolage', and 'proactive real-time innovation'. Everything seems to depend on observing and reading the changing circumstances and determining what appears to be the next play. The strategy of 'coordination and collaboration' is an important tool for critically

evaluating current practices and adapting and innovating in response to emerging problems and challenges.

Platform organizations offer one possible architecture for enabling, supporting, and combining the different robustness strategies. Ciborra (1996) first introduced the idea of a platform organization, building on the example of the Italian firm Olivetti. He argued that Olivetti operated as a platform that organized and reorganized different projects to respond to changing needs and opportunities. He noted that platform organizations operate as bricoleurs that constantly use and reuse different organizational forms to respond to turbulence, surprise, and opportunity. Platforms can help to rapidly assemble and support purpose-built organizations, such as task forces, networks, partnerships, etc. (Ansell & Gash, 2018; Ansell & Miura, 2020).

Polycentricity is another possible architecture for promoting robust governance of turbulence. This concept refers to semi-autonomous decision centers that take each other into account (Carlisle & Gruby, 2019). Anderies and Janssen (2013) and Capano and Woo (2018) argue that a polycentric system helps to incorporate and combine the diversity, modularity, and flexibility necessary for developing robust policies. Building on the work of Ostrom on the management of the commons, polycentricity seeks to combine the advantages of local self-governance with nested multi-level governance.

When analyzing the choice and combination of robustness strategies, special attention should be paid to the question of *the failure to act robustly in the face of turbulence*. The responsible governance actors may—for apparently ‘good reasons’—overinvest in a particular response to turbulence that creates a future lock-in by limiting the scope for adaptation and innovation. They may also be so shocked and paralyzed by the sudden emergence of an unexpected crisis and a rising turbulence that their capacity to act, let alone act proactively, is limited. Finally, interdepartmental conflicts, political dictates from above, or legal and institutional constraints may prevent governance actors from acting robustly, despite their recognition of the need to think outside the box to deal with heightened turbulence.

Last, yet importantly, the choice and combination of robustness strategies may be different at distinct levels and in different jurisdictions and the problems and/or benefits of that variability deserve careful analysis. Moreover, with the arrival of poly-crisis and the simultaneous expansion of turbulence in different sectors, spheres, and contexts, we may also want to know whether different combinations of robustness strategies in different problem settings collide, reinforce one another, or are relatively unconnected.

6. Evaluating the impact of the efforts to forge robust governance responses

There is no guarantee that the robustness strategies chosen by a group of governance actors match the turbulent situation; nor is it certain that the strategies are successfully implemented. *The appropriateness of the selected robustness strategies* is likely to depend on whether they are supported by a well-informed situational analysis, practical reasoning based on experience and learning, and credible and well-communicated justification strategies. The appropriateness of a governance strategy should be evaluated vis-à-vis its normative context (March and Olsen, 1995), but the evaluation must also look at cognitive aspects such as the range and quality of available data, the supply of adequate information and relevant knowledge, and the back-and-forth movement between

facts, norms, and strategy formulations. Strategic appropriateness may also depend on the practical reasoning of upstream and downstream actors and how this reasoning is integrated into robustness strategies. The final test of strategic appropriateness is whether the strategies are communicated to relevant audiences and accompanied by story lines that justify the chosen strategies with reference to the normative context, the analysis of the situation and perhaps the national governance tradition.

It is also worth exploring whether and how *the implementation of the chosen robustness strategies* depends on the presence of broad-based support from epistemic communities, interest organizations and affected segments of the population. Many strategies are jeopardized by the accumulation of social and political resistance. At least in liberal democratic countries, governments have difficulties launching unpopular strategies, even in times of crisis and turbulence where the question for order and normalcy may overshadow discussion of the content of particular solutions. However, resistance can often be mitigated by means of a combination of consultations, concessions, and adjustments. Here multivocality plays a key role. The same robustness strategy may be communicated differently to different audiences stressing different elements.

A last thing to explore is the extent to which the chosen *robustness strategies are continuously adapted* to new and changing circumstances and whether they exploit emerging opportunities for bouncing forward and developing responses in ways that help to achieve strategic policy goals. Some robustness strategies may stall due to blindness to new and unexpected developments or because the supporting actors protect a joint agreement out of fear that the costs of reaching a new agreement will be exceedingly high. Continuous adaptation and innovation may be achieved by means of a combination of open-access dashboards providing updated documentation of problems and challenges, procedures for regular evaluation and adjustment of the course of action and the use of modulization that allows decisionmakers to turn up and down for the use of different modules.

Robust governance may fail in the early stages of strategy formulation and strategy implementation due to unpreparedness, confusion and lack of knowledge on the part of the key actors, but eventual some more or less appropriate strategies will be formulated and implemented, although they will continue to be subject to subsequent adjustments and reinventions. These situations—as well as other situations where the formulation and execution are less successful—beg the question of whether implemented robustness strategies produce the expected outcomes by contributing to maintain core public functions, goals, and values. The impact analysis should not aim to assess the optimality of one particular robustness strategy since turbulence is a moving target characterized by great uncertainty that require trial and error and constant strategic changes. In addition, we should bear in mind that each robustness strategy comes with a series of trade-offs between positive and negative effects that are likely to change over time.

Nevertheless, the *litmus test of robust governance* will be whether one or more robustness strategies contribute to upholding core public functions, goals, and values in the face of turbulence in an effective and legitimate way. Where effective robustness strategies are detected, it is important to carefully describe the evolving course of actions that they triggered and to track the results and impacts. Since there are often trade-offs between the effectiveness and legitimacy of a robustness strategy, the social and political support for the strategy should also be assessed. Finally, it would be interesting to see how governance actors draw lessons based on their own evaluative practices and compare these lessons with the insights derived from a research-based assessment of the same robustness strategies. Robustness strategies that work in practice and can be backed by independent research may feed forward to build capacities for robust governance in the future.

7. A robust mindset in support of robust governance

Organizations, sectors, regimes and systems may be more or less robust in the sense of withstanding external shocks. However, the key ambition of the ROBUST project is not to measure varying degrees of robustness perceived as a property of particular units, but rather to improve the ability of public governors to respond robustly to turbulence. Public governors may choose between different combinations of robustness strategies that in different ways promote adaptation and innovation, but using these strategies requires a robust mindset. If your mind is set for maintaining stability, control and risk aversity, the prospect for robust governance is dim.

Public governors act based on a particular mindset defined as beliefs that shape how you make sense of the world, yourself and your actions. It influences how public governors think, feel, and behave in a situation of heightened turbulence (Yeager and Dweck, 2012). If public governors are steeped in bureaucratic thinking focused on compliance or New Public Management goals of effectiveness and efficiency, they will have a hard time adjusting to the demands for robust governance in turbulent times. Hence, in order to improve the ability of the public sector to deal robustly with turbulent problems and situations, public governors need to cultivate a robust mindset, i.e., a mindset that allows public governors to face turbulence without wavering, flexibly adapt policy, regulation and services and proactively innovate solutions to match the unpredictable dynamics in their environment.

Facing heightened turbulence is tough since it appears that the ground is shaking and moving and everything is falling apart. Moreover, public governors will tend to feel disempowered as they realize that traditional coping strategies such as prediction, forecasting and protection do not work in the face of turbulence. So, what can they do?

Denial of rising turbulence is not an option since the upholding of core public functions, objectives and values are at stake. The same goes for lapsing into a state of despair that will also prevent a swift response. Instead, public governance must embrace turbulence and realize that disruption is not an exceptional state of affairs that will soon disappear, but rather the new normal. Public governors must learn to live with turbulence by seeing themselves as the stable center of a semi-permanent turbulent environment that generates changing and unpredictable problems and challenges that they must respond to. They must diagnose the emerging problems and challenges vis-à-vis the core functions, goals and values that are expected to uphold, and in doing so they should look for the new possibilities. Hence, it might be that the COVID-19 pandemic has led to growing unemployment, but government may respond by generating jobs in the new green energy sector rather than in the old black fossil fuel sector. Robust governance aims to exploit crisis-induced turbulence to create solutions that are both different and better than the old solutions.

Robust governance calls for adaptation to new and changing events, demands and developments that may interact in unforeseen ways and create all kinds of disruption. Adapting well-established solutions to new conditions in a volatile environment requires a flexible mindset. A *fixed mindset* avoids challenges and refuses to deviate from the set path. A *flexible mindset* calmly observes sudden changes, considers what the room of manoeuvring for adaptation, and is unafraid to suggest changes in existing mechanisms, routines and services in response to unpredictable dynamics. A flexible mindset is akin to a growth mindset in the sense that it is guided by the belief that one's skills and

competences are malleable and can and will change in tandem with changes in governance and external contexts (Dweck, 2016).

A robust mindset must not only be flexible but also *innovative* in the sense of welcoming innovation (Sidhu, Goubet and Xia, 2016). An innovative mindset will tend to have focus on the creation of value for citizens and society at large, even in situations of crisis and socioeconomic constraint. It will be open to inputs that can help to better understand the problems and challenges at hand and inspire the development of new solutions. It puts a premium on creativity and the ability to imagine that there are more than one way of achieving a particular function, goal or value. It accepts the risk of failure but aims to fail fast and inexpensively by developing and testing prototypes in small scale before scaling. It supports learning based on experience and dialogue. Finally, an innovative mindset is visionary in the sense of pursuing grand visions while knowing that the road may be long and winding and full of sudden problems that call for invention of new solutions on the fly.

A robust mindset is also characterized by the ability to tolerate *cognitive dissonance* (Harmon-Jones and Mills 2019). In turbulence situations, different types of information and knowledge may contradict each other and also challenge existing beliefs and time pressure will tend to prevent further cognitive clarification. Moreover, the strategic interventions aiming to solve one problem may unintentionally create another problem that must then be solved through adaptation and innovation. Accepting this result may require a tolerance for a particular *strategic dissonance* that shows itself in the presence of trade-offs, paradoxes and dilemmas.

An additional set of *qualities of a robust mindset* can be gleaned from the robustness strategies that tend to presuppose a new way of thinking. The new and important qualities inherent to a robust mindset can be condensed into eight dictums:

1. Think of slack and redundancies as valuable resources rather than waste
2. Value strategic openness that expands future options
3. Think in futures and be prepared for surprise
4. Praise exceptionality rules and requisite variation
5. Focus on the need to scale operations and resources
6. Think in modules and repurposing
7. Improvise instead of panicking
8. Value and cultivate trust-based relations

Cultivating a robust mindset in the public sector is no easy task. The ways public officials are thinking is shaped by the governance orthodoxy that combines bureaucratic values with key elements of the New Public Governance (Torfing, 2023). However, evaluation of the experiences of dealing with the current multi-crisis combined with leadership training may set a new robustness agenda for public governors. Our hope is that the ROBUST project can contribute to the much-needed change.

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